

Model Primary School Standards and Student Learning Outcomes in Cambodia: The Roles of Teacher Capacity, Leadership, and Parental Engagement

Theara Tang
Postgraduate School, National University of Battambang, Cambodia

Abstract

Improving the quality of education remains a pressing challenge in Cambodia, where access to schooling has expanded, but learning outcomes, particularly in Khmer and mathematics, remain weak. To address these challenges, the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sport introduced the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS), a reform framework designed to strengthen teaching, leadership, accountability, and community engagement. Despite its policy importance, there is a lack of empirical evidence on how MPSSs are implemented in practice and its impact on teachers, students, and parents. This research aimed to assess the effect of the Model Primary School System initiative in Pailin Province. The study was based on a foundation of social, cognitive, sociocultural, expectancy-value, and leadership theories. Ultimately, the study determined how the model primary school system influences crucial educational elements, including teacher capabilities, leadership styles, parental engagement, students' self-perceptions, and the resulting outcomes.

Keywords: *Educational Management, Student Learning Outcomes, Model Primary School Standards (MPSS), Quality Education.*

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Introduction

In this context, improving the quality of education remains one of the most pressing challenges in global development. Moreover, access to schooling has expanded dramatically, and many children, especially those in low- and middle-income countries, complete several years of primary education without mastering foundational skills such as literacy and numeracy (Akyeampong & Fofack, 2019). This learning crisis has highlighted the need for reforms that focus not only on access but also on teaching quality, school leadership, and system accountability.

Cambodia has made steady progress in expanding primary education, achieving near-gender parity and high enrollment rates. Nevertheless, concerns about quality persist. National and international assessments continue to show weak student performance, particularly in Khmer language and mathematics, alongside high dropout rates in rural areas (Benveniste et al., 2008; UNESCO, 2022). These challenges pose a threat to the country's efforts to strengthen human capital, reduce poverty, and build a more equitable society. In response, the Royal Government of Cambodia has identified education as a core pillar of its Pentagonal Strategy–Phase I (Royal Government of Cambodia, 2023). Within this vision, the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sport (MoEYS) introduced the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS). The MPSS is designed to create schools that are more inclusive, accountable, and effective in delivering meaningful learning. Despite this policy framework, limited research has examined how MPSSs

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are implemented in practice, how they shape teaching and leadership, and how they influence student outcomes and parental engagement. This study responds to that need, focusing on schools in Pailin Province as a case that reflects both urban and rural realities.

The objective of this study is to examine how the implementation of the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) influences student learning outcomes in Cambodian primary schools by analyzing the interrelated roles of systemic and institutional factors, sustainable leadership for learning, parental engagement, and student self-perceptions. Specifically, the study seeks to investigate how MPSS and related policy support shape teacher autonomy and self-efficacy, foster effective leadership practices, and strengthen parental expectations and involvement and how these factors, in turn, affect students' academic self-concept, self-esteem, and academic performance in the Khmer language and mathematics. In addition, the study aims to explore whether these relationships vary according to contextual conditions, particularly school location (urban versus rural), thereby providing a nuanced understanding of how standard-based reforms operate across diverse educational settings. Through this integrated perspective, the study intends to contribute empirical evidence to the literature on school effectiveness and education reform in developing country contexts while offering policy-relevant insights into how the MPSS can be leveraged to promote equitable and sustainable improvements in primary education quality in Cambodia.

Literature Review

Introduction

This paper examines the body of literature that provides the foundation for the study of the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) in Cambodia. It draws on theoretical, empirical, and policy perspectives to situate the research within broader debates about teacher quality, school leadership, parental engagement, student self-perceptions, and the contextual challenges that shape learning outcomes. At the same time, it considers Cambodia's ongoing reform agenda and how the MPSS reflects wider regional and global trends in education.

The review serves several purposes. It first introduces the conceptual and theoretical perspectives that frame the study, highlighting how learning, motivation, and leadership theories help explain the factors influencing teaching and learning in primary schools. It then brings together international and regional evidence on standards-based reforms with a particular focus on how teacher capacities, leadership practices, parental involvement, and student self-perceptions are linked to educational outcomes. Ultimately, it highlights gaps in existing knowledge of the Cambodian context, particularly regarding the role of MPSS in addressing quality and equity issues.

The discussion developed gradually, beginning with theoretical foundations, before considering international experiences and ultimately focusing on Cambodia. Each of the central themes, teacher professional capacities, leadership and systemic support, student self-perceptions and academic achievement, parental expectations and involvement, and contextual influences such as gender and school location, is explored in turn. The chapter concludes with a synthesis of the literature into a conceptual framework that underpins the research design.

Through this process, the review connects directly to the study's aim of understanding how the MPSS contributes to student learning outcomes in Cambodian primary schools.

Global, Regional, and National Perspectives on Education Quality and Learning Reform

Global and Regional Perspectives on Education Quality and Learning Outcomes

Over the past two decades, the global education agenda has evolved from expanding school access to improving the quality and equity of learning outcomes. While access to education has widened dramatically, the persistent gap between years of schooling and actual learning achievements, which is often referred to as the global learning crisis, has drawn increasing attention from scholars and policymakers (Auld et al., 2019; Hanushek & Woessmann, 2009). Hanushek and Woessmann (2009)

demonstrated through cross-country analyses that cognitive skills, rather than mere school attainment, are the primary drivers of national productivity and long-term economic growth. Their findings show that a one standard deviation increase in test scores on international assessments such as the PISA or TIMSS corresponds to an approximately 2 percent rise in annual per capita GDP growth. This means that the quality of education in terms of how many students learn has greater macroeconomic implications than does the quantity of schooling alone. The Programs for International Student Assessment (PISA), conducted every three years by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), evaluates how well 15-year-old students are prepared for life and further learning. The 2018 cycle, which included over 70 participating economies, focused primarily on reading literacy while also assessing mathematics, science, and broader indicators such as school climate, student motivation, and well-being. Findings from the PISA 2018 Results (Volume III), titled “What School Life Means for Students’ Lives,” revealed that students who report strong teacher support, a sense of belonging, and positive relationships with peers perform better academically and experience greater life satisfaction. Conversely, bullying, low engagement, and weak teacher–student relationships are associated with poorer outcomes (Summaries, 2018).

These results emphasize that academic success and well-being are mutually reinforcing goals and that improving education quality requires addressing both learning outcomes and the emotional and social dimensions of schooling. In the Asia–Pacific region, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) highlighted the importance of transforming traditional education systems into lifelong learning societies. Its report, *Powering Learning Society During an Age of Disruption* (Ra et al., 2021), underscores that the ability to “learn how to learn” is critical for individuals to remain resilient amid the technological shifts of Industry 4.0, demographic changes, and postpandemic recovery. Building such learning societies requires education systems that cultivate cognitive, digital, and socioemotional competencies across the lifespan, thereby promoting adaptability, innovation, and inclusive growth.

Education Quality, Learning, and Reform in South Asia

The South Asian experience illustrates that rapid expansion in educational access has not automatically translated into better learning. Despite significant gains in enrollment since the early 2000s, learning outcomes in the region have remained among the lowest globally. The World Bank’s *Student Learning in South Asia* (Dundar et al., 2014) revealed that many students complete primary education without mastering basic reading and numeracy skills. In India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nepal, national and independent assessments consistently show that a large proportion of students cannot solve simple arithmetic problems or comprehend grade-level texts. This disconnect between schooling and learning is rooted in systemic challenge. Teacher absenteeism, inadequate instructional time, and weak accountability mechanisms remain pervasive across the region (Dundar et al., 2014). Teachers’ subject knowledge and pedagogical skills are often limited, and political interference in recruitment or deployment undermines merit-based professional systems. The report concludes that teacher quality, which includes relevant preparation, motivation, and professional accountability, is the single most influential school-level factor shaping student outcomes.

The findings align with Hanushek and Woessmann’s (2008) global evidence on the quality of learning, especially in terms of foundational literacy, numeracy, problem solving, and central sustainable economic growth. They also resonate with the OECD’s (2019) insights that education systems performing well globally combine academic rigor, teacher professionalism, and student well-being. To address these challenges, countries in South Asia are increasingly embracing the idea of building learning societies. The ADB framework (Ra et al., 2021) advocates for integrated ecosystems that connect schools, communities, and industries to sustain lifelong learning.

This approach promotes flexible curricula, technology-enabled assessments, and cross-sectoral partnerships. By linking formal education with informal and vocational learning, such reforms can strengthen both employability and social inclusion across diverse populations.

Cambodia's Education Reform, Learning Society, and Quality Assurance Systems

Model primary school standards (MPSS): Policy basis and purpose

Within the context of Cambodia's ongoing education reform agenda, efforts to strengthen school quality and student learning outcomes have necessitated clearer expectations, shared accountability, and practical tools for school-level improvement. In alignment with these national priorities, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport (MoEYS) introduced the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) as a formal quality framework for public primary schools. The MPSS framework is designed to support key school reform objectives, including enhanced learning outcomes, a strengthened school culture, and explicit expectations regarding discipline, ethics, and professional conduct.

From the perspective of educational management, the MPSS is significant because it advances beyond general policy statements by offering a structured set of standards and evidence-based expectations to guide school planning, implementation, monitoring, and improvement. The framework is intended to assist schools, local authorities, and communities in developing a shared understanding of the characteristics that define a quality primary school, particularly in relation to instructional processes, management practices, stakeholder participation, and accountability.

MPSS structure: Five standards and their management relevance

The MPSS is organized into five standards that describe the core areas of school performance:

- 1) Student Learning Outcomes
- 2) Teaching and Learning
- 3) Community Participation
- 4) School Operations and Administration
- 5) School Accountability

These five standards are highly relevant to the present dissertation, as they reflect the primary functions commonly emphasized in educational management research: the improvement of teaching and learning, the strengthening of professional practice and leadership, the development of effective school–community relationships, the assurance of efficient administration and resource utilization, and the promotion of transparency and accountability.

Importantly, the five standards also provide a coherent policy lens through which school improvement can be understood as an integrated system—in which instructional quality depends not only on teacher capacity but also on leadership, planning, community support, and accountability mechanisms that shape teaching and learning conditions.

Indicators, subindicators, and benchmarks

To operationalize the five standards, the MPSS framework employs indicators and subindicators that specify observable evidence of implementation. The structure comprises 26 indicators and 71 subindicators distributed across the five standards, enabling schools to identify strengths and gaps in specific performance areas. Additionally, the MPSS defines benchmark levels, which may be qualitative or quantitative depending on the indicator. For school leaders and education managers, this structure is significant because it clarifies the types of evidence needed, such as planning documents, monitoring practices, teaching and learning support activities, participation mechanisms, and accountability or reporting practices. Consequently, the MPSS serves as both a guidance framework and a monitoring tool to facilitate continuous school development in a consistent and transparent manner.

MPSS evaluation logic and improvement orientation

The MPSS also establishes a results verification and scoring system designed to evaluate evidence across standards. The framework specifies an overall scoring approach with a total of 355 points (representing 100 percent) and sets a threshold (e.g., 249 points or above) to determine whether a school has met MPSS

requirements. The evaluation process emphasizes documenting and verifying evidence for each indicator, as well as summarizing performance by standard and overall scores. Beyond the scoring mechanism, the MPSS embodies a broader orientation toward continuous improvement. The model-school concept emphasizes practical expectations, including accountability to the community, enhanced school-based planning and implementation, professional development for management and teachers, the use of assessment data to improve teaching and support all learners, and active parent and community participation in school development. These features are closely aligned with the principles of school effectiveness and continuous improvement in educational management.

Boundary and scope

Although the MPSS provides the national quality framework for Cambodian primary schools, this dissertation does not seek to assess schools' compliance with the MPSS criteria or to produce an MPSS performance rating. The MPSS is used here as a contextual reference framework to describe how quality is formally defined and operationalized in Cambodia. The analytical focus of the study is instead to examine how MPSS-related domains, student outcomes, teaching and learning, community participation, school operations, and accountability can be interpreted through the five theoretical perspectives presented in the next section. In this way, the MPSS informs the study's framing, whereas the theories provide explanatory pathways for understanding the relationships investigated in this dissertation.

Teachers' Professional Capacity

The quality of any education system depends fundamentally on the quality and professional capacities of its teachers. Effective teachers not only master subject and pedagogical knowledge but also demonstrate professional judgment, ethical commitment, and continual learning to meet the complex demands of teaching. As global and national education systems move to competency-based and lifelong learning frameworks, strengthening teachers' professionalism and capacity becomes a cornerstone of educational improvement (Collinson, 1999; Hopkins & Stern, 1996; UNESCO, 2022). In Cambodia, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport (MoEYS) prioritized teacher professionalization through the introduction of model training institutions, career-path frameworks, and continuous professional development (CPD) systems (MoEYS, 2025).

Teacher autonomy and professional identity

Teacher professionalism relies on autonomy, reflective practice, and an ethical commitment to student learning. Hopkins and Stern (1996) argued that quality schools emerge when teachers are empowered to act as decision makers, collaborate to solve instructional problems, and share responsibility for student success. Collinson (1999) similarly redefined teacher excellence as an evolving synthesis of moral purpose, intellectual curiosity, and collegial engagement rather than mere adherence to bureaucratic standards.

These conceptions of professionalism resonate strongly with Cambodia's Model School Standards, which call for teachers to participate in school self-assessment, engage communities, and publicly report learning results (Ministry of Education, 2023). Within such systems, autonomy means exercising informed professional judgment within a culture of shared accountability, and teachers are trusted to innovate while remaining aligned with school and community goals.

Self-Efficacy, Resilience, and Professional Growth

A teacher's belief in their ability influences learning, notably self-efficacy, which is central to professional growth and resilience. Bandura (1997) identified self-efficacy as the foundation of human agency: confident teachers persist longer, adopt more effective strategies, and respond to challenges constructively. Empirical evidence extends this insight beyond classroom outcomes to long-term student trajectories. Chetty et al. (2014) reported that teachers with high value-added scores consistently improve student test performance and significantly increase their students' future earnings and college attendance. Papay and Kraft (2015) further demonstrated that teachers continue to grow in effectiveness throughout their careers when they work in supportive and collaborative environments. In Cambodia, the current reform mirrors these findings. The Education Congress Report 2023--2024 noted the expansion of CPD

systems and the adoption of teacher career pathways designed to recognize professional development and performance (MoEYS, 2025). These initiatives aim to nurture teacher confidence, resilience, and motivation and ensure that educators remain adaptive contributors to a learning society.

Assessment Literacy and Data-Informed Practice

Teachers' capacity to interpret assessment evidence and adjust instruction accordingly is integral to instructional quality. Black and Wiliam (1998) demonstrated that formative assessment, which uses a feedback guide for the next steps, produces substantial learning gains, especially among lower-achieving students. Popham (2009) emphasized that assessment literacy is an essential professional skill, requiring teachers to understand what assessments measure and how to use results to enhance learning. Volante and Fazio (2007) added that teacher education must explicitly prepare candidates to apply assessment data to instructional decision-making. In Cambodia, standardized testing and school-based assessment embedded in the Model School Standards and participation in regional assessments such as the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 illustrate a growing commitment to data-informed practice (MoEYS, 2025). Teachers are increasingly expected to use results to identify learning gaps, plan remediation, and communicate progress to stakeholders. The development of assessment literacy thus strengthens both teaching effectiveness and accountability.

Professional development, coaching, and professional learning communities

Sustained improvement in teaching depends on well-designed professional learning. Timperley, Wilson, Barrar, and Fung (2007) reported that professional development (PD) has the greatest impact when it is continuous, collaborative, and explicitly linked to student outcomes. Desimone (2009) identified five essential PD features, such as content focus, active learning, coherence, duration, and collective participation, that enhance effectiveness. These approaches, such as instructional coaching, mentoring, and professional learning communities (PLCs), exemplify these principles by enabling teachers to observe, reflect, and refine practice together. Cambodia's CPD reforms and regional mentoring networks incorporate ideas, positioning teachers not only as recipients of training but also as active agents of change and shared learning (MoEYS, 2025). Teachers' effectiveness has long been identified as one of the strongest influences on student achievement.

The research details the most powerful factors at the school level influencing student learning results, such as the quality of the teacher, specifically, their expertise, skill setting, and professional demeanor (Darling-Hammond, 2000; Nilsen & Gustafsson, 2016). However, effective teachers are flexible enough to adapt their methods, self-assured enough to handle diverse classrooms, and skilled at using assessments to improve their instruction. Throughout their careers, these educators never stop learning and reflecting on their practice (Burroughs et al., 2019; Engida et al., 2024).

Research highlights several capacities that are particularly important. Teacher independence (autonomy) and self-confidence (self-efficacy) are key factors in innovation and perseverance, especially when working in difficult educational settings (Hopkins & Stern, 1996). Furthermore, assessment literacy, which refers to an educator's ability to create relevant tests and use the results to improve their teaching, is a vital component of high-quality instruction (Burroughs et al., 2019). Evidence from low- and middle-income countries further underscores the value of structured, evidence-based teaching practices, such as lesson facilitation, real-time feedback, and attention to socioemotional development (Carter et al., 2024). Teachers collaborate and share responsibility for learning, which produces stronger results and particularly benefits disadvantaged students (Heck, 2007). However, teacher capacity in Cambodia remains constrained by significant systemic challenges.

Progress is continuously obstructed by factors such as staff shortages, the unequal deployment of qualified teachers between urban and rural areas, low salaries, and insufficient access to high-quality professional development (Benveniste et al., 2008; MoEYS, 2023). These difficulties mirror the problems observed in many low- and middle-income nations, namely, weak initial teacher education, fragmented ongoing training, and minimal classroom support, ultimately limiting the success of educational reforms (E. Akyeampong & Fofack, 2019).

The Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) were launched to address these systemic challenges. The framework sets clearer expectations for instruction, connects professional practice directly to student learning, and strengthens accountability. By emphasizing teacher autonomy (independence), self-efficacy (self-confidence), assessment literacy (data use), and collaborative professionalism (teamwork), the MPSS seeks to create a supportive environment that enables teachers to significantly improve student learning.

Instructional Quality and Classroom Processes

Instructional quality represents the direct link between teachers' professional capacities and students' learning experiences. It encompasses the clarity of teaching, cognitive challenges, the classroom climate, and the alignment between the curriculum, time, and opportunity. Decades of research affirm that teaching quality is one of the most powerful school factors influencing student achievement (Hattie, 2009; Nilsen & Gustafsson, 2016). In Cambodia, improving instructional practices is the center of school-based reform, with model schools expected to exemplify effective pedagogy, inclusion, and continuous improvement (MoEYS, 2023; 2025).

Clarity of Instruction and Formative Feedback

The clarity of explanations and constructive feedback are hallmarks of effective instruction. Brookhart (2011) noted that teachers must translate curriculum goals into explicit learning targets, communicate success criteria, and provide feedback that enables students to close performance gaps. Transparent communication and timely feedback help students link new concepts with prior knowledge and take ownership of their learning.

Cambodia's Model Primary School Standards encourage these practices by requiring teachers to use formative assessments and provide continuous feedback to support diverse learners (MoEYS, 2023). These evidence-based approaches confirm that clarity and feedback, when embedded in everyday teaching, significantly enhance student learning.

Cognitive Activation and Higher-Order Learning

High-quality instruction not only transmits knowledge but also increases learners' capacity for reasoning, analysis and problem solving. Baumert et al. (2010) demonstrated that teachers with deep content and pedagogical knowledge are better able to design cognitively demanding lessons that sustain student engagement and conceptual understanding. Building on this, Hattie's updated synthesis and visible learning. Sequel (2023) offers the most comprehensive empirical evidence on the factors influencing student achievement. Drawing from over 2,100 meta-analyses, 130,000 studies, and data on 400 million learners, Hattie (2023) emphasized that nearly all educational interventions yield some improvement, yet the real question is "what works best", that is, which conditions maximize impact across diverse contexts? The revised visible learning model situates teaching and learning as an intentional alignment of learning intentions, success criteria, assessment, and feedback guided by teachers' expertise and evaluative thinking.

One of the major conceptual advancements in 2023 is the focus on mind frames in terms of the beliefs and evaluative habits that shape how teachers think about and respond to learning evidence. Rather than prescribing a set of fixed strategies, Hattie (2023) contends that effective teaching arises from a mindset of continual reflection, feedback, and adjustment. He further underscores the importance of collective teacher efficacy, defined as educators' shared belief that their collective capacity positively affects students. These factors consistently demonstrate one of the greatest impacts on learning outcomes across global datasets. The new synthesis refines the benchmark for educational impact, reporting an average effect size of 0.42, slightly above the 0.40 "hinge points" identified in the 2009 edition, and indicating the threshold for meaningful improvement in learning. Hattie's findings confirm that instructional clarity, formative feedback, and cognitive challenges remain among the most powerful influences on student achievements, but these effects are magnified when teachers act as evaluators of their own impact and collaborators within professional learning communities (Hattie, 2023).

In Cambodia, these insights resonate with MoYES's (2022; 2025) emphasis on strengthening science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education and cultivating reflective, data-driven teaching cultures. The emphasis on teacher mindsets and collective efficacy closely aligns with current national reforms that promote professional collaboration, inquiry-based learning, and reflective practice, thereby enhancing classroom quality and student outcomes.

Classroom Management and Supportive Climate

A well-managed, supportive classroom environment enables learning to flourish. Nilsen and Gustafsson (2016), analyzing data from the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), reported that classrooms characterized by trust, clear expectations, and positive relationships achieve higher cognitive outcomes across countries. Effective classroom management, therefore, combines structure with emotional safety and respect. Cambodia's Model School Standards emphasize discipline, morality, and positive behavior (MoEYS, 2023), aligning with this evidence. Teachers are encouraged to build climates that balance high expectations with empathy, ensuring that all students, including those from marginalized backgrounds, can engage meaningfully in learning.

Opportunity to Learn, Instructional Time, and Curriculum Alignment

Opportunity to learn (OTL) refers to students' exposure to the intended curriculum under adequate instructional conditions. Empirical evidence indicates that time-on-task strongly predicts learning outcomes. Cattaneo, Oggenfuss, and Wolter (2017) documented additional instructional hours associated with measurable improvements in performance, whereas long-term analyses of international assessments highlight the role of curriculum coherence and alignment between instruction and testing (Mullis et al., 2016).

In Cambodia, MoEYS (2025) continues to expand instructional time by addressing teacher absenteeism, promoting full-day schooling, and refining curriculum sequencing. Ensuring equitable opportunities to learn through both sufficient time and curriculum relevance remains essential for sustaining national progress in learning outcomes.

Leadership Models and Educational Outcomes

Leadership is a critical determinant of educational quality and improvement. Over the past three decades, leadership research has evolved from a focus on management and control to emphasize influence, values, collaboration, and learning. Effective leadership is now widely recognized as second only to classroom teaching in its impact on student achievement (Bush & Glover, 2014; Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006). Leadership is another crucial lens through which to view this study. Transformational leadership emphasizes vision, inspiration, and capacity building, whereas distributed leadership highlights collaboration and shared responsibility (Hopkins & Stern, 1996; Leithwood & Jantzi, 2005). Both perspectives align with MPSS principles that call for participatory governance, fair management, and active community engagement. They emphasize that strong and supportive leadership is crucial for motivating teachers, fostering professional cultures, and sustaining improvements in student outcomes. Taken together, these theories explain why MPSS focuses not only on teacher training and the curriculum but also on leadership development, parental involvement, and student well-being. They highlight the interconnectedness among individual beliefs, classroom practices, and systemic support, providing a strong conceptual basis for this study's research questions and hypotheses.

Evolving Models of Educational Leadership

Early leadership models were managerial and centered on organizational efficiency and administrative control. These approaches were gradually supplemented and, in many cases, replaced by models that positioned teaching and learning at the core of leadership practice. Instructional leadership emphasizes leaders' direct involvement in curriculum design, teacher development, and assessment. Bush and Glover (2014) noted that leaders who engage in teacher learning and curriculum coordination have a significantly stronger impact on student outcomes than those whose role is limited to administration. Transformational leadership further advances this concept by inspiring staff through vision, motivation,

and shared commitment. It aims to increase teachers' and students' collective sense of purpose and responsibility. However, critics caution that transformational leadership may risk becoming overly top-down if teachers are not genuinely engaged in decision-making (Bush & Glover, 2014). Consequently, distributed leadership emerged as a more inclusive model that redistributes influence among teachers, departments, and teams. Empirical research indicates that when leadership responsibilities are shared and supported, schools experience stronger collaboration, innovation, and student learning outcomes (Bush & Glover, 2014; Hallinger & Heck, 2010).

Leadership as an Organizational Property

In addition to individual leaders, effective schools also demonstrate leadership as an organizational property. This property is a collective capacity embedded in the school's culture and systems. Heck (2007) reported that teacher quality, conceptualized as a school-level characteristic encompassing qualifications, instructional practices, and collective competence, significantly predicts both student achievement levels and growth rates. His findings further reveal that such organizational properties can reduce inequities related to socioeconomic status and ethnicity. This perspective aligns with the view that leadership must extend beyond the principal to build systemic structures that support teacher collaboration, data-informed decision-making, and professional learning. Hallinger (2011) and Robinson et al. (2008) emphasized that leadership for learning is most effective when it integrates an instructional focus with relational trust and shared accountability. In Cambodia, this orientation is reflected in the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport (MoEYS) initiatives, such as the Model School Standards and Education Congress reforms, which promote collaborative governance and mentoring systems that strengthen both leadership and teaching quality (MoEYS, 2025).

Sustainable Leadership, Organizational Justice, and School Well-Being

As educational systems face growing pressures from globalization, digital transformation, and social inequality, sustainability becomes an essential dimension of leadership. Sustainable leadership focuses on long-term improvement, preserving and strengthening human, social, and environmental resources rather than depleting them (Hargreaves & Fink, 2006). It emphasizes ethical stewardship, collective capacity, and the continuity of leadership across generations.

Sustainable leadership and institutional development

Recent studies define sustainable leadership as a model that integrates educational and social sustainability principles into decision-making and organizational culture. Rosário and Boechat (2025) argue that sustainable leadership aligns ethical responsibility with long-term institutional value, balancing profitability and performance with fairness, inclusion, and stakeholder well-being. Their analysis identified seven key dimensions of sustainability in leadership: depth of learning, continuity, distribution of responsibility, justice, diversity, resource conservation, and the preservation of human well-being. Similarly, Eustachio et al. (2024) examined higher education institutions and reported that sustainability leadership (SL) has a strong direct effect on embedding sustainability into teaching practices, whereas transformational leadership (TL) does not have a significant direct effect when it is tested simultaneously. This suggests that while transformational leadership contributes to motivation and vision, sustainable leadership ensures deeper institutional change through reflective practice, equity, and systemic alignment. Together, these findings affirm that sustainable leadership combines ethical intent with strategic foresight, ensuring that educational development remains inclusive and enduring.

Organizational Justice, Retention, and Collective Efficacy

A sustainable, educational system also depends on fairness within its organizational structures. Zhou and Ma (2022) demonstrated that organizational justice, which is the perception of fairness in procedures, interactions, and outcomes, significantly reduces teachers' turnover intentions. Their study showed that salary satisfaction partially mediates this relationship, indicating that fair compensation and transparent management practices enhance teacher commitment and morale. In Cambodia, similar priorities have been embedded in MoEYS reforms, which emphasize transparent teacher evaluation systems, merit-based promotions, and fair compensation practices (MoEYS, 2025). When teachers perceive justice and

respect within their schools, collective efficacy strengthens to contribute to higher retention and improved instructional quality, both of which are vital to sustainable reform.

Sustainable leadership, families, and communities

Sustainable leadership also extends beyond schools by nurturing partnerships with families and communities. Wilder's (2014) meta-synthesis of nine meta-analyses revealed a consistent, positive relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement, especially when involvement reflects parental expectations and encouragement. In contrast, the effect of homework assistance was weaker and sometimes negative. These findings underscore the need for leaders to facilitate meaningful parental engagement focused on dialog, trust, and shared responsibility for learning. Cambodia's ongoing shift toward school-based management and community participation mirrors these principles. By integrating family engagement, community partnerships, and teacher empowerment, sustainable leadership fosters a resilient educational ecosystem that links social justice with long-term educational quality (MoEYS, 2022; 2025; UNESCO, 2022).

Learning Attitudes, Engagement, and Teacher–Student Relationships

Students' learning attitudes and engagement are shaped by far more than individual motivation; they develop through the quality of relationships, classroom interactions, and the emotional tone of schooling. Learning, as Pianta, Hamre, and Allen (2012) described, is a relational process. Engagement, whether cognitive, emotional, or behavioral, emerges when teachers build supportive relationships, set clear expectations, and structure learning environments that make students feel seen, capable, and valued. From this perspective, effective teachers do more than deliver content. They help students interpret challenges as opportunities, provide feedback that guides improvement, and foster classroom trust. When this relational and instructional support is strong, students are more likely to persist, regulate their learning, and feel confident in their abilities (Pianta et al., 2012).

International evidence reinforces these patterns. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018 reported that students who reported greater teacher support, a stronger sense of belonging, and positive peer relations achieved greater reading performance and reported greater well-being (Auld et al., 2019). Conversely, students who experienced frequent bullying or negative disciplinary climates tended to perform worse and disengaged from school. These findings reveal that belonging, respect, and fairness are not peripheral to learning; rather, they are essential conditions for motivation and achievement.

Teacher–student relationships are particularly powerful when combined with instructional clarity and feedback. Hattie's Visible Learning meta-analysis (2009) synthesized hundreds of studies and concluded that the most effective teaching strategies are those that make learning visible, that is, when goals, progress, and success criteria are clearly communicated and when students receive continuous feedback to guide improvement. When teachers think evaluatively about their own impact, adjusting instruction in response to student evidence, engagement, and achievement increases dramatically.

Family involvement further strengthens engagement. Jeynes's (2007) meta-analysis covering 52 studies of urban secondary students demonstrated that parental involvement, particularly in the form of high expectations, encouragement, and communication about school, has a significant and positive effect on academic outcomes, roughly half a standard deviation in magnitude. Importantly, not all involvement is equal: guidance, discussion, and emotional support are consistently more beneficial than strict monitoring or control (Jeynes, 2007). In short, students' learning attitudes flourish when they feel connected to teachers, peers, and families who believe in their potential. Engagement grows from classrooms that combine emotional support with academic challenges, where effort is recognized, and relationships are grounded in respect. In Cambodia's ongoing education reforms, the emphasis on learner-centered pedagogy and a positive school climate aligns closely with this evidence, reinforcing the idea that the social fabric of schooling is inseparable from its academic goals.

Educational Equity, Quality, and Learning Gaps

Educational equity remains one of the central challenges in achieving quality learning for all. Across global and regional studies, achievement gaps persist along social, economic, and geographic lines even within systems that have achieved near-universal access to schooling. The PISA 2018 underscored that while many countries have improved average performance, wide disparities remain between advantaged and disadvantaged students, particularly in reading. Systems that succeed both academically and equitably tend to share one trait: they ensure that every student, regardless of background, has access to capable teachers, sufficient learning time, and supportive learning environments (OECD, 2019).

Unequal Foundations and early literacy

Inequality in learning often begins in the earliest grades, where children either acquire or fail to acquire foundational skills. Evidence from the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) shows that in many developing countries, a majority of Grade 2 pupils cannot even read a single word of a short passage, a pattern that threatens later learning across subjects (Gove & Wetterberg, 2011). These results, drawn from dozens of national EGRA applications, show that early reading proficiency is the gateway to lifelong learning: children who fail to read fluently by Grade 3 rarely recover academically. However, targeted interventions such as phonics-based instruction, structured materials, and teacher coaching have demonstrated rapid improvements in literacy outcomes when systematically implemented.

Time, Opportunity, and Instructional Conditions

Time in school matters, but how that time is used matters even more. Using data from more than 50 countries, Lavy (2010) reported that an additional hour of weekly instruction in core subjects was associated with approximately 0.15 standard deviation higher test scores in developed contexts, although these scores were lower in developing settings. Crucially, these gains were larger where schools had autonomy and accountability systems, enabling teachers to use instructional time effectively.

However, increasing instructional time alone cannot close learning gaps unless teachers are prepared to use it effectively. Akyeampong et al. (2013) demonstrated that initial teacher education in several African countries heavily emphasized content mastery over pedagogy, leaving new teachers confident yet underprepared to teach early reading and mathematics. When teachers lack the pedagogical tools to engage learners or connect lessons to understand, more hours simply reproduce existing inequalities rather than reduce them.

Geography, Resources, and Structural Disparities

Geographic and social inequalities in learning remain pronounced. In Peru, Rojas Apaza et al. (2024) reported a substantial urban–rural mathematics performance gap of more than 60 points in national assessments, with approximately 82% of the disparity explained by observable factors such as socioeconomic status and school resources. This pattern mirrors evidence from other developing contexts, where rural schools often have fewer qualified teachers, larger class sizes, and limited access to materials or technology.

In addition to the quantity of resources, the quality of teaching and early opportunities to learn are decisive. Studies in sub-Saharan Africa have shown that poorly designed teacher education and inadequate classroom support produce cohorts of students who attend school but fail to master basic competencies (K. Akyeampong et al., 2013). Likewise, EGRA studies reveal that improving teaching quality at the foundation stage can yield transformative gains for disadvantaged learners (Gove & Wetterberg, 2011). Policy implications point to a consistent lesson: equity and quality are inseparable. Systems narrow learning gaps when they act early (strengthening literacy and numeracy foundations), use time purposefully (ensuring attendance and effective instruction), and target resources toward the most disadvantaged schools. In Cambodia and other Southeast Asian contexts, this means combining model school standards with targeted teacher development, literacy initiatives, and community partnerships to ensure that every learner, urban or rural, rich or poor, has a fair opportunity to learn.

Assessment and Monitoring Systems

Strong assessment and monitoring systems enable education sectors to understand how well students are learning, how teachers are teaching, and how effectively policies translate into classroom practice. They operate at three interconnected levels: international benchmarking, regional and national diagnosis, and classroom-based formative assessment.

International Learning Assessments

Large-scale international assessments such as the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) provide comparative benchmarks for learning quality and equity.

Findings from the TIMSS 2019 show that while overall performance in mathematics and science has improved worldwide, major within-country gaps remain, largely linked to instructional time, teacher preparation, and school resources (IEA, 2020; Plomp & Loxley, 2020). Likewise, the PISA 2018 revealed that systems that combine high achievement with equity, such as Finland and Singapore, share key features. These components are clearly defined standards, consistent teacher support, and positive school climates (OECD, 2019).

For Cambodia, participation in the PISA 2025 and the adoption of the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) represent major steps toward evidence-based system improvement. These tools help identify learning bottlenecks and connect classroom practices to international expectations. Moreover, the UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report (2023) warns that while digital and adaptive assessments expand access to data, technology must serve teachers, not replace them. Assessment should continue to focus on human learning and teacher judgment, not solely on digital performance indicators (UNESCO, 2023).

Regional tools: SEA-PLM and EGRA

Regional and early-grade assessment initiatives complement global monitoring by generating locally relevant evidence. The Southeast Asia primary learning metric (SEA-PLM) measures the proficiency of Grade 5 students in literacy, numeracy, and global citizenship. Its 2019 cycle revealed wide disparities across and within ASEAN member states but also documented strong links between teacher quality, the home learning environment, and student attitudes.

The early-grade reading assessment (EGRA) serves as a diagnostic tool to measure foundational literacy. Studies by RTI International (2020) and Gove and Wetterberg (2011) show that targeted interventions, such as teacher coaching, structured phonics, and leveled readers, produce rapid literacy gains when supported by continuous monitoring. Cambodia's application of SEA-PLM and EGRA data has directly informed the MPSS and the national literacy policy, prioritizing Grade 3 reading fluency as the cornerstone of later achievement.

Classroom-level assessment literacy and MPSS alignment

Assessment and monitoring are most effective when teachers can interpret and act on evidence in real time. Research by Black and Wiliam (1998) and Brookhart (2011) demonstrates that formative assessment—clarifying learning goals, providing feedback, and adjusting instruction—can double the rate of student learning, particularly among lower achievers.

The MPSS operationalizes these insights by embedding classroom-based assessment indicators within its teaching-and-learning domain. Teachers are encouraged to design assessments that diagnose learning needs, communicate progress to students and parents, and use results to refine instruction. This aligns with the national goal of building teachers' assessment literacy and creating a feedback-rich culture that links classroom practice to national and international benchmarks.

Conceptual and Theoretical Foundations

This study is guided by several theoretical perspectives that help explain how teaching, leadership, parental support, and student beliefs interact to shape learning outcomes. Together, they provide the conceptual framework for examining how the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) aim to enhance education quality in Cambodia.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Influence of Model Primary School Standards (MPSSs) on Student Learning Outcomes

Social Cognitive Theory

Bandura's social cognitive theory emphasizes self-efficacy as a central factor influencing human action (Bandura, 1997). Applied to education, teacher self-efficacy refers to the confidence that teachers have in their ability to motivate students and manage classrooms effectively. Research shows that teachers with higher self-efficacy are more likely to adopt creative methods, persist with struggling students, and create supportive learning environments (Gibson & Dembo, 1984; Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001). This perspective is directly relevant to MPSS, which aims to strengthen teacher capacities through clear standards, training, and accountability.

Sociocultural Theory

Vygotsky's sociocultural theory emphasizes the social nature of learning, particularly the roles of interaction, scaffolding, and the zone of proximal development in promoting student learning (Vygotsky, 1978). Piaget's earlier work also emphasized the importance of active engagement with the environment in cognitive development (Piaget & Cook, 1952).

These ideas support the MPSS emphasis on interactive pedagogy, peer tutoring, and school–community collaboration, suggesting that student growth is best achieved through guided participation and shared responsibility.

Expectancy Value Theory

Expectancy-value theory explains student motivation as a function of their belief in their ability to succeed and the value they place on learning tasks (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002). Students who see themselves as capable and view schoolwork as meaningful are more engaged and perform better. Pintrich and colleagues (1993) extended this perspective by linking motivation to the use of effective learning strategies. This theory is important for understanding how MPSS initiatives influence students' academic self-concepts and self-esteem and how these, in turn, affect performance in subjects such as Khmer and mathematics.

Multiple intelligences theory

Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences broadens the definition of ability beyond linguistic and mathematical domains to include interpersonal, intrapersonal, musical, spatial, and bodily kinesthetic skills (Gardner, 1983). Later interpretations highlight the importance of creativity and of adapting teaching to different learning styles (Morgan, 2021). This view aligns with MPSS, which advocates for inclusive and holistic approaches by promoting life skills, ICT use, and extracurricular activities alongside traditional subjects.

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate how Model Primary School Standards (MPSSs) influence teaching, leadership, parental engagement, and student learning outcomes in Cambodian primary schools, with Pailin Province serving as a case study that reflects both urban and rural realities. The findings suggest that the MPSS has made meaningful contributions to improving teacher capacity, strengthening leadership practices, and encouraging parental involvement while also highlighting essential differences across locations and genders that continue to constrain equity. Teachers emerged as central agents of change. Their autonomy, self-efficacy, and assessment literacy were significantly enhanced under MPSS; however, these capacities were stronger in urban schools, where resources and training were more readily available. Leadership was also shown to be a decisive factor: principals who practiced fairness, collaboration, and shared responsibility motivated teachers and fostered professional growth. However, limited leadership preparation and the dual burdens of teaching and administration have reduced the sustainability of these practices. Moreover, future research should broaden the scope beyond a single province, adopt longitudinal approaches to track the sustainability of reforms, and explore the less-studied domains of the MPSS, such as governance and financing. Greater attention to gendered patterns of self-belief and achievement would also contribute to more nuanced and responsive interventions.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflicts of interest exist.

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